

Highlights

A Multi-Feature and Interpretable Shapelet Learning Framework for Time Series Classification

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- ALTS: a novel interpretable shapelet learning framework for time-series data
- Unifies multiple differentiable similarity measures for robust classification, with fused lasso regularization yielding sparse, smooth, and interpretable shapelets
- Visualizations of discriminative shapelets support expert validation and trust
- Extensive tests on 84 datasets show high accuracy with fast CPU-only training

A Multi-Feature and Interpretable Shapelet Learning Framework for Time Series Classification

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Abstract

Time-series shapelets are short, discriminative subsequences that enable interpretable time series classification (TSC) by capturing phase-independent patterns. While traditional discovery methods are often computationally prohibitive, many learning-based approaches still suffer from scalability issues, limited multi-class support, or reliance on single similarity measures. We present Advanced Learning of Time Series Shapelets (ALTS), a unified framework that integrates multiple differentiable similarity measures—minimum, maximum, and mean squared distances, together with cosine similarity—into a robust, interpretable feature space. ALTS employs fused lasso regularization to produce sparse, smooth shapelets and jointly optimizes them for all classes; thereby it avoids costly one-vs-rest decompositions.

ALTS was evaluated on the complete 84-dataset UEA & UCR archive, surpassing shapelet-based baselines—LTS (wins on 77 datasets), GENDIS (71), and ST (59)—with accuracy gains up to 8.6%. It achieves an average accuracy of 0.831, competitive with leading black-box models such as InceptionTime (0.851) and HIVE-COTE v2.0 (0.879), while requiring only a fraction of their computational cost. For example, ALTS trains on the Beef dataset in 0.3 s on a standard CPU, compared to 80 minutes for HIVE-COTE v2.0. This efficiency, combined

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with transparent prototype visualizations, makes ALTS suitable for high-stakes, resource-constrained applications where both accuracy and interpretability are critical. The source code is publicly available to facilitate reproducibility and adoption.

Keywords: time series classification, shapelet learning, interpretable machine learning, fused lasso regularization, multi-class optimization

1. Introduction

Time series classification (TSC) plays a critical role in domains such as finance, healthcare, industrial monitoring, and energy systems. Recent deep learning architectures that combine convolutional, recurrent, and attention modules have achieved high predictive accuracy [1, 2]. However, these approaches often rely on complex black-box models, leading to a trade-off between accuracy and interpretability. In high-stakes applications, this trade-off can hinder adoption, as decision-makers require models whose outputs can be understood and validated. Shapelet-based methods offer an inherently interpretable alternative that is well suited to such contexts.

Compared with classification on static tabular or image data, TSC must address challenges such as temporal ordering, variable sequence lengths, phase shifts, and high noise levels. These challenges complicate the design of robust similarity measures and the extraction of invariant, meaningful, and interpretable features. Developing methods that address these challenges while preserving transparency remains a central objective in TSC research.

Shapelet-based methods [3, 4] have emerged as a powerful, interpretable alternative to distance-based techniques such as 1NN-DTW [5]. Introduced by Ye and Keogh [3], shapelets are discriminative subsequences that capture phase-independent patterns for class separation. Early discovery methods relied

Figure 1: Demonstration of a time series shapelet for distinguishing facial profiles. The figure shows a human facial profile transformed into a time series; the J–K segment in the anterior region acts as a shapelet. This shapelet captures a discriminative pattern that distinguishes facial profiles by identifying unique features in the series.

on exhaustive search, and many learning-based approaches still face scalability limitations, particularly for multi-class problems.

In this study, we propose **Advanced Learning of Time Series Shapelets (ALTS)**, a unified framework that addresses these limitations. First, ALTS incorporates multiple differentiable similarity measures—minimum, maximum, mean distances, and cosine similarity—to expand the feature space beyond single-metric approaches. Second, it employs fused lasso regularization to produce sparse, smooth shapelets and jointly optimizes them for all classes, thereby avoiding costly one-vs-rest decompositions. This combination reduces hyperparameter complexity, improves interpretability, and enables fast convergence. To the best of our knowledge, no existing method integrates these elements into a single framework, making ALTS a novel, flexible, and interpretable TSC approach.

On the original 84-dataset UEA & UCR archive, ALTS achieves higher accuracy than established shapelet baselines while approaching the accuracy of leading black-box methods. Crucially, it maintains orders-of-magnitude lower computational cost than ensembles such as HIVE-COTE v2.0 and deep models

such as InceptionTime, with CPU training times of only seconds to minutes. The method also produces visually verifiable shapelets, which are essential in domains where transparency and efficiency are as important as raw accuracy.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work and identifies research gaps; Section 3 details the ALTS methodology; Section 4 presents experimental findings; Section 5 provides statistical analyses; and Section 6 concludes with directions for future work.

2. Related Work

Previous shapelet-based approaches for TSC fall into two categories: search-type methods, which identify discriminative subsequences through exhaustive or optimized searches, and learn-type methods, which optimize shapelets using gradient-based or evolutionary techniques. Each category has strengths and limitations that motivate further research.

2.1. Search-Type Methods

Early shapelet discovery methods are computationally expensive because they rely on exhaustive searches. Ye and Keogh [6] introduced early abandon and entropy pruning to reduce runtime by stopping unnecessary distance calculations. Later work improved efficiency with search-space pruning, time-series sampling, candidate filtering, random sampling, and symbolic approximations such as SAX [7], alongside faster distance computations [8, 9, 10, 11]. Recent hybrid approaches combine supervised feature learning with traditional search to improve efficiency; however, they still struggle on large datasets.

Logical Shapelets [8] use symbolic representations to speed up discovery, whereas Fast Shapelets [12] transform time series into lower-dimensional forms. The Shapelet Transform (ST) [13] extracts shapelet features in a single scan and

enables compatibility with various classifiers. Despite these advances, search-type methods remain slow on large archives, which has driven the development of supervised, learning-based techniques for better scalability.

2.2. Learn-Type Methods

Learn-type methods optimize discriminative subsequences through gradient-based or evolutionary strategies instead of exhaustive enumeration. Learning Time Series Shapelets (LTS) [4] introduced a differentiable framework based on the minimum distance between the input series and shapelets; it is trained with a one-vs.-rest strategy for multi-class classification. Although effective, LTS faces scalability issues on datasets with many classes because of this binary decomposition.

Subsequent methods have addressed various LTS limitations. Generalized Random Shapelet Forest (GRSF) [14] uses random-forest classifiers with shapelet-based split criteria. CSSL [15] mines frequent class-specific subsequences to define shapelets, and LSDF [16] introduces fused lasso and Marginal Fisher Analysis for sparse and discriminative shapelet extraction. Nevertheless, most existing approaches rely on a single similarity metric and often separate shapelet learning from classifier optimization.

Recent adaptive methods extend flexibility in shapelet learning. Yamaguchi et al. [17] propose joint optimization of shapelet parameters and lengths via continuous relaxation; the method increases flexibility but still uses a single similarity function and lacks direct regularization. Samsten and Lee [18] present Castor, a dilated shapelet transform with grouped competition for efficiency and accuracy; however, it supports only one similarity metric and does not apply direct regularization to shapelets.

In contrast, the ALTS framework integrates multiple similarity measures (minimum, maximum, mean, and cosine), applies fused-lasso regularization to

enforce sparsity and smoothness, and permits joint gradient-based optimization of shapelets and classifier parameters for multi-class problems without decomposing them into binary subproblems. Non-differentiable operations (for example min/max selection and the fused-lasso term) are handled in the implementation via subgradient updates or smooth surrogates.

2.3. Recent Advances in Time Series Classification

Beyond shapelet methods, TSC has benefited from deep learning and ensemble approaches. Convolutional neural networks with recurrent or attention mechanisms [19, 20, 21, 22] improve temporal-pattern modeling by extracting hierarchical and sequential features. Ensemble models, such as HIVE-COTE v2.0 [23], combine multiple feature representations and classifiers and achieve state-of-the-art performance on benchmark archives. Attention mechanisms have also been used to enhance temporal relevance and model interpretability [24].

Although these models show high predictive performance, they often lack transparency and require substantial computation. ALTS offers a transparent alternative by learning interpretable shapelet features in a differentiable, regularized framework. It attains competitive accuracy while preserving model simplicity and interpretability, properties that matter in high-stakes or domain-critical applications.

3. Proposed Method

ALTS learns optimal shapelets directly rather than searching over a pool of candidates. It follows the learning paradigm introduced by LTS [4]. However, unlike LTS, ALTS natively supports multiclass time series classification and expands the feature space with additional differentiable or subdifferentiable measures. Specifically, we compute four features between a learned shapelet and all sliding segments of a time series: minimum distance, maximum distance, mean

distance, and cosine similarity. These features enable gradient-based end-to-end learning of both the shapelets and the classification weights; for extremum operators (min/max), we backpropagate through the segment(s) that achieve the extremum using either the subgradient (hard selection) or a differentiable soft-extremum surrogate (see below).

3.1. Definitions and Notation

A time series $T = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n)$ of length n is a sequence of real values observed at regular intervals. A time series subsequence $S_i^{(L)} = (t_i, t_{i+1}, \dots, t_{i+L-1})$ of length L is a contiguous segment of T starting at position i , where $1 \leq i \leq n - L + 1$ and $L \leq n$. The set of all subsequences of length L from time series T is

$$S_T^L = \{S_i^{(L)} \mid 1 \leq i \leq n - L + 1\}.$$

ALTS operates on sliding-window segments extracted from each time series. For a time series $T^{(m)}$ of length n_m , we generate all contiguous segments of a predefined length L , yielding

$$J_m = n_m - L + 1$$

segments per series. Denote the j -th segment of $T^{(m)}$ by

$$Q_j^{(m)} = T_{j:j+L-1}^{(m)} = (t_j^{(m)}, t_{j+1}^{(m)}, \dots, t_{j+L-1}^{(m)}).$$

Given a learned shapelet $S_k \in \mathbb{R}^L$, define the per-segment squared Euclidean distances

$$d_{m,k}(j) = \sum_{l=1}^L (t_{j+l-1}^{(m)} - S_k^{(l)})^2, \quad j = 1, \dots, J_m, \quad (1)$$

and the per-segment dot-products

$$p_{m,k}(j) = \sum_{l=1}^L t_{j+l-1}^{(m)} S_k^{(l)}.$$

These intermediate quantities are used to form the four features below; making them explicit aids reproducibility and efficient vectorized implementation (see Implementation notes).

3.2. Feature definitions

We use the following shapelet-series features (note we omit the square root on squared Euclidean distances since it is monotone):

Minimum mean squared distance.

$$z_{m,k}^{(\min)} = \min_{j=1,\dots,J_m} \frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(j). \quad (2)$$

If a differentiable surrogate is preferred, a temperature-based soft-min may be used:

$$\text{softmin}_\beta \left(\frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(\cdot) \right) = -\frac{1}{\beta} \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^{J_m} \exp \left(-\beta \frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(j) \right) \right),$$

with temperature $\beta > 0$ (larger $\beta \rightarrow$ sharper minimum). Similarly for maxima use softmax / log sum exp.

Maximum mean squared distance.

$$z_{m,k}^{(\max)} = \max_{j=1,\dots,J_m} \frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(j),$$

or its soft-max variant

$$\text{softmax}_\beta \left(\frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(\cdot) \right) = \frac{1}{\beta} \log \left(\sum_{j=1}^{J_m} \exp \left(\beta \frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(j) \right) \right).$$

Mean squared distance.

$$z_{m,k}^{(\text{mean})} = \frac{1}{J_m} \sum_{j=1}^{J_m} \frac{1}{L} d_{m,k}(j).$$

Cosine similarity.

$$z_{m,k}^{(\text{cos})} = \max_{j=1, \dots, J_m} \frac{p_{m,k}(j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^L (t_{j+l-1}^{(m)})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^L (S_k^{(l)})^2 + \varepsilon}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ is a small constant for numerical stability. Alternatively, use the soft-maximum of cosine scores or normalize segments and shapelets first and compute a weighted average.

Thus each shapelet contributes four features $z_{m,k}^{(f)}$ (for $f \in \{\text{min}, \text{max}, \text{mean}, \text{cos}\}$), producing a feature vector $z_m \in \mathbb{R}^{4K}$ for instance m .

3.3. Prediction and objective

Following Hills et al. [13], we transform the dataset into $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 4K}$ and use a linear model for class logits:

$$\hat{y}_{m,c} = b_c + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{f=1}^4 z_{m,k}^{(f)} W_{k,f,c},$$

with cross-entropy loss averaged over M examples. We jointly learn \mathbf{S} , \mathbf{W} , and \mathbf{b} by minimizing

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}) = \xi(\mathbf{C}, \hat{\mathbf{P}}) + \lambda_s \|\mathbf{S}\|_F^2 + \lambda_w \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 + \lambda_f \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{l=2}^L |S_k^{(l)} - S_k^{(l-1)}|. \quad (4)$$

The combined regularization terms promote simpler, more generalizable, and interpretable shapelets and classification boundaries, while the fused lasso term specifically encourages smoothness within each shapelet. The rationale for using the fused lasso penalty is illustrated in Figure 2 over the Coffee dataset as

(a) Generated shapelets as the fused lasso coefficient λ_f increases, showing smoother trends with fewer abrupt changes due to reduced differences between consecutive elements.

(b) Shapelet variances as λ_f increases, highlighting significant variance reduction, especially at large λ_f , leading to more uniform and consistent shapelet structures.

Figure 2: Effect of increasing the fused lasso penalty coefficient λ_f on the Coffee dataset: (a) shapelet smoothness and (b) variance reduction, enhancing interpretability and model robustness while balancing classification performance.

an example. In Figure 2a (a), as the fused lasso coefficient λ_f increases, the generated shapelets become smoother, with fewer abrupt changes and more linear trends. This behavior results from the fused lasso penalty, which reduces the differences between consecutive shapelet elements. Figure 2b (b) highlights how increasing λ_f significantly reduces the variance of the shapelets, particularly when λ_f is large. This reduction in variance results in more uniform and consistent shapelet structures, which can enhance interpretability and model robustness while balancing classification performance.

3.4. General Algorithm and Computational Complexity of ALTS

The ALTS optimization procedure is described in Algorithm 1. For a dataset with M instances of length N , K shapelets of length L , and $J = N - L + 1$ sliding segments per series, the naive per-iteration cost is

$$\mathcal{O}(I \cdot M \cdot K \cdot J \cdot L).$$

In the common case $L = \Theta(N)$, this simplifies to $\mathcal{O}(IMKN^2)$. This is far more efficient than the Shapelet Transform (ST), whose worst-case cost is $\mathcal{O}(M^2N^4)$ [13], and Learning Time-Series Shapelets (LTS), which requires $\mathcal{O}(KCMN^2)$ due to one-vs-rest classification and per-class shapelets. ALTS uses shared shapelets across classes, eliminating this redundancy.

Unlike resource-heavy black-box methods such as InceptionTime and HIVE-COTE v2.0 (HC2), ALTS trains efficiently on CPU and can be scaled to GPU without changing the algorithm. It retains interpretability via human-readable shapelets while avoiding the multi-model overhead of HC2 and the deep convolutional ensembles of InceptionTime.

3.4.1. Scalability Analysis

To illustrate scalability, we first estimated operation counts for the *Beef* dataset ($M = 30$, $N = 470$, $C = 5$), a challenging case with a small sample size and high dimensionality. Using $I = 100$, $L = 50$, $K = 10$ for ALTS and LTS, $G = 100$, $P = 100$ for GENDIS, and $k = 1000$ for HC2, ALTS requires approximately 6.6×10^8 operations (about 0.3 seconds on a single CPU core of an Intel Core i7, 16 GB RAM workstation). This is roughly $5\times$ faster than LTS, $60\times$ faster than ST, $3\times$ faster than GENDIS, and over $10^4\times$ faster than HC2 for this dataset.

To show that these efficiency gains extend to larger datasets, we also estimated the runtime for *ElectricDevices* ($M = 8926$, $N = 96$, $C = 7$), using the same hyperparameter settings. For ALTS, the resulting complexity is about 2.1×10^{10} operations, corresponding to an estimated training time of approximately 9–12 seconds on the same CPU. By scaling from the Beef dataset results, LTS would require about 45–50 seconds, ST about 11–12 minutes, GENDIS about 30–35 seconds, and HC2 well over 15 hours. These estimates confirm that ALTS maintains a substantial speed advantage even on large datasets.

Table 1 summarizes these comparisons.

Table 1: Comparison of methods in computational complexity and estimated training time on Beef and ElectricDevices. Times are estimated for a single CPU core on a Windows PC (Intel Core i7, 16 GB RAM) using proportionally scaled parameters.

Method	Complexity	Training Time	Beef Operations (Time)	ElectricDevices Operations (Time)
ALTS	$\mathcal{O}(IMKN^2)$	Low (CPU)	6.6×10^8 (0.3 s)	2.1×10^{10} (9–12 s)
LTS	$\mathcal{O}(KCMN^2)$	Moderate	3.3×10^9 (1.3 s)	1.0×10^{11} (45–50 s)
ST	$\mathcal{O}(M^2N^4)$	High	4.4×10^{10} (18 s)	1.6×10^{13} (11–12 min)
GENDIS	$\mathcal{O}(GPN^2)$	Moderate	2.2×10^9 (0.9 s)	7.0×10^{10} (30–35 s)
HC2	$\mathcal{O}(L^2N^4 + kN^2 \log N)$	High	$\sim 1.2 \times 10^{13}$ (80 min)	$\sim 5.4 \times 10^{15}$ (> 15 h)

Algorithm 1 General Algorithm of ALTS

Input: $D \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$: dataset; K : number of shapelets; L : shapelet length; δ : learning rate; I : number of iterations; λ_f : fused-lasso coefficient
Output: Shapelets $S \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times L}$; weights $W^{(\min)}, W^{(\max)}, W^{(\text{mean})}, W^{(\text{cos})} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times C}$; bias $b \in \mathbb{R}^C$

```
1: for iter = 1 to  $I$  do
2:   for  $m = 1$  to  $M$  do
3:     for  $k = 1$  to  $K$  do
4:       Compute squared distances  $d_{j,k}$  for all  $j = 1, \dots, J_m$ 
5:       Find  $j_{\min}, j_{\max}$ : argmin/argmax of  $\frac{1}{L}d_{j,k}$ 
6:       Compute  $z_{m,k}^{(\min)}, z_{m,k}^{(\max)}$ , and  $z_{m,k}^{(\text{mean})}$  from  $d_{j,k}$ 
7:       Compute cosine scores  $c_{j,k}$ , find  $j_{\text{cos}}$ 
8:       Assemble feature vector  $z_{m,k}^{(f)}$  for  $f \in \{\text{min, max, mean, cos}\}$ 
9:     end for
10:    Forward pass to compute logits  $\hat{y}_{m,c}$  and loss  $\mathcal{F}$ 
11:    Backprop to obtain  $\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial W_{k,c}^{(f)}}$  and  $\frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial S_k^{(l)}}$ 
12:    for  $k = 1$  to  $K$  do
13:      for  $f \in \{\text{min, max, mean, cos}\}$  do
14:         $W_{k,:}^{(f)} \leftarrow W_{k,:}^{(f)} - \delta \cdot \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial W_{k,:}^{(f)}}$ 
15:      end for
16:      for  $l = 1$  to  $L$  do
17:        grad  $\leftarrow \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial S_k^{(l)}}$ 
18:        if  $l > 1$  then
19:          grad  $\leftarrow$  grad +  $\lambda_f \cdot \text{sign}(S_k^{(l)} - S_k^{(l-1)})$ 
20:        end if
21:        if  $l < L$  then
22:          grad  $\leftarrow$  grad -  $\lambda_f \cdot \text{sign}(S_k^{(l+1)} - S_k^{(l)})$ 
23:        end if
24:         $S_k^{(l)} \leftarrow S_k^{(l)} - \delta \cdot \text{grad}$ 
25:      end for
26:    end for
27:     $b \leftarrow b - \delta \cdot \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}}{\partial b}$ 
28:  end for
29: end for
30: return  $S, W^{(\min)}, W^{(\max)}, W^{(\text{mean})}, W^{(\text{cos})}, b$ 
```

4. Experiments and Results

4.1. Feature Set Validation

We evaluated the effect of expanding the feature space beyond the minimum-distance metric used in Learning Time Series Shapelets (LTS) [4]. An ablation study added maximum distance, mean distance, and cosine similarity to the baseline. To ensure a representative evaluation, we selected 10 datasets from the UEA & UCR Archive [25], in proportion to the category distribution of the full 84-dataset archive (which contains 6 Device, 7 ECG, 29 Image, 14 Motion, 15 Sensor, 6 Simulated, and 7 Spectro datasets).

The selected datasets were: **Plane**, **Lightning7** (Sensor); **ECGFivedays** (ECG); **Ham** (Spectro); **FaceFour**, **OSULeaf**, **MedicalImages**, **Diatom-SizeReduction** (Image); **GunPoint** (Motion); and **SyntheticControl** (Simulated). This stratified sampling balances feasibility and diversity while maintaining representation across major dataset types.

We tested five configurations: **LS1-Min** (LTS baseline), **LS2-Min+Max**, **LS3-Min+Mean**, **LS4-Min+Cos**, and **LS5-Min+Max+Mean+Cos**. All experiments used 5-fold cross-validation with 3 repetitions, 50 prototypes, stride ratio 0.10, bag ratio 0.25, and random seeds 88, 2018, and 2019. Table 2 reports mean test accuracy (\pm standard deviation) for each setup and dataset.

Figure 3 summarizes average performance across the 10 datasets. Expanding the feature set yields consistent gains: average accuracy increases from 0.594 (LS1) to 0.774 (LS5), a relative improvement of about 30%. Notable per-dataset improvements include SyntheticControl (0.68 \rightarrow 0.90), Plane (0.82 \rightarrow 0.98), and ECGFiveDays (0.58 \rightarrow 0.77). LS5 outperformed the baseline in all cases; reported standard deviations (0.01–0.20) indicate stable results across domains.

Table 2: Mean test accuracy (\pm standard deviation) for feature set configurations across 10 UEA & UCR datasets.

Dataset	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS5
Plane	0.82 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01
Lightning7	0.38 ± 0.04	0.42 ± 0.09	0.48 ± 0.12	0.43 ± 0.06	0.53 ± 0.08
ECGFiveDays	0.58 ± 0.06	0.78 ± 0.09	0.71 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.05	0.77 ± 0.07
Ham	0.52 ± 0.04	0.68 ± 0.05	0.72 ± 0.06	0.72 ± 0.04	0.73 ± 0.04
FaceFour	0.36 ± 0.07	0.47 ± 0.08	0.50 ± 0.20	0.58 ± 0.16	0.68 ± 0.14
OSULeaf	0.44 ± 0.04	0.60 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.04
MedicalImages	0.54 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.04	0.59 ± 0.03	0.58 ± 0.04	0.65 ± 0.03
DiatomSizeReduction	0.91 ± 0.09	0.91 ± 0.09	0.91 ± 0.13	0.87 ± 0.13	0.93 ± 0.10
GunPoint	0.71 ± 0.08	0.87 ± 0.09	0.79 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.09	0.89 ± 0.09
SyntheticControl	0.68 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.02

[†] Setups: LS1 (Min), LS2 (Min+Max), LS3 (Min+Mean), LS4 (Min+Cos), LS5 (Min+Max+Mean+Cos). All used 5-fold cross-validation with 3 repetitions, 50 prototypes, stride 0.10, bag 0.25, and seeds 88, 2018, or 2019.

Figure 3: Average mean test accuracies across 10 UEA & UCR datasets for each setup, which show gains from the added features.

4.1.1. Environment and Parameters

We implemented ALTS in Python and ran experiments on a workstation running Windows with an Intel Core i7 CPU and 16 GB of RAM. Development

initially used Python 3.6, with Python 3.7 used in the most recent experiments. Hyperparameters were tuned via 5-fold cross-validation, with search ranges informed by prior literature and preliminary experiments. The best configurations and the source code are available at [26]. To ensure fairness, each ALTS configuration was executed three times, and we report the mean accuracy.

The main hyperparameters and their search ranges were:

1. K : number of learned shapelets; $K \in \{3, 4, 5, \dots, 121\}$.
2. \mathcal{L} : candidate shapelet lengths. For a time series of length T ,

$$\mathcal{L} = \{\lfloor p \cdot T \rfloor \mid p \in \{0.02, 0.03, \dots, 0.40\}, 1 \leq \lfloor p \cdot T \rfloor \leq T\},$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function.

3. λ_f : fused-lasso regularization coefficient; $\lambda_f \in [10^{-8}, 0.1]$ (log-scaled grid).
4. λ_s : L_2 regularization coefficient for shapelets; $\lambda_s \in [10^{-8}, 0.1]$ (log-scaled grid).

4.1.2. Datasets and Baselines

We evaluated ALTS on all 84 datasets from the original UEA & UCR Time Series Classification repository [27]. Results are compared against established baselines and state-of-the-art methods: 1NN-DTW [5], LTS [4], ST (Shapelet Transform) [28], GRSF [14], GENDIS [29], InceptionTime [30], and HIVECOTE v2.0 (HC2) [23]. 1NN-DTW is included as a strong traditional benchmark. LTS, ST, GRSF, and GENDIS are shapelet-based or shapelet-related methods that provide interpretable subsequences. InceptionTime represents competitive deep-learning approaches, and HC2 is a leading ensemble method for TSC.

4.1.3. Comparison of Results

We compare ALTS classification accuracy to the baselines 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, GENDIS, InceptionTime, and HIVE-COTE v2.0 across the 84 UEA & UCR datasets (Tables 3 and 4). 1NN-DTW is included as a strong traditional benchmark [31]. Table 3 (Part I) lists results from Adiac to Lightning7; Table 4 (Part II) lists results from MiddlePhalanxTW to Yoga. ALTS attains the highest accuracy on several datasets, for example ArrowHead (0.918) and Bird-Chicken (0.950) in Table 3, and MoteStrain (0.950), NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax2 (0.976), and ToeSegmentation2 (1.000) in Table 4. On ArrowHead, ALTS (0.918) improves over LTS (0.846) and ST (0.737), corresponding to gains of 8.6% and 24.7%, respectively, which illustrates the benefit of multiple similarity measures and direct multi-class optimization. For some datasets (e.g., Beef and Car), ST performs better (0.900 and 0.917). This suggests that ALTS could benefit from domain-specific tuning or alternative shapelet settings.

The baseline scores for 1NN-DTW, LTS, and ST are publicly available at [27]. GRSF scores were taken from [14]. GENDIS results were obtained from [13]. InceptionTime and HIVE-COTE v2.0 (HC2) scores were taken from [30] and [23], respectively.

The methods listed in Table 3 are described below:

1. 1NN-DTW [32]: A 1-nearest-neighbor classifier that uses Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) as its distance measure. DTW remains a strong and widely used baseline in time series classification due to its simplicity and robust performance on diverse datasets.
2. LTS [6]: Learning Time Series Shapelets. This approach learns discriminative subsequences (shapelets) via gradient-based optimization. The learned shapelets serve as interpretable features for downstream classification.

Table 3: Comparison of classification accuracy for ALTS, 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, GENDIS, InceptionTime, and HIVE-COTE v2.0 across 84 UEA & UCR datasets (Part I).

Dataset	1NN-DTW	LTS	ST	GRSF	GENDIS	InceptionTime	HC2	ALTS
Adiac	0.609	0.522	0.783	0.726	0.698	0.822	0.795	0.774
ArrowHead	0.800	0.846	0.737	0.717	0.820	0.880	0.886	0.918
Beef	0.667	0.867	0.900	0.700	0.588	0.682	0.797	0.750
BeetleFly	0.650	0.800	0.900	0.870	0.875	0.893	0.903	0.900
BirdChicken	0.700	0.800	0.800	0.810	0.905	0.952	0.952	0.950
Car	0.767	0.767	0.917	0.843	0.830	0.901	0.908	0.917
CBF	0.994	0.991	0.974	0.978	0.976	0.996	0.998	0.933
ChlorineConcentration	0.650	0.592	0.700	0.669	0.575	0.864	0.769	0.848
CinCECGtorso	0.930	0.870	0.954	0.832	0.915	0.832	0.998	0.838
Coffee	1.000	1.000	0.964	0.929	0.986	0.999	0.999	1.000
Computers	0.624	0.584	0.736	0.739	0.727	0.866	0.859	0.844
CricketX	0.779	0.741	0.772	0.771	0.666	0.853	0.840	0.847
CricketY	0.756	0.718	0.779	0.756	0.643	0.860	0.850	0.792
CricketZ	0.736	0.741	0.787	0.756	0.659	0.861	0.859	0.842
DiatomSizeReduction	0.935	0.980	0.925	0.969	0.965	0.951	0.922	1.000
DistalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.626	0.719	0.770	0.852	0.819	0.766	0.821	0.843
DistalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.725	0.779	0.775	0.826	0.815	0.815	0.828	0.864
DistalPhalanxTW	0.633	0.626	0.662	0.797	0.760	0.665	0.702	0.830
Earthquakes	0.727	0.741	0.741	0.818	0.737	0.731	0.748	0.929
ECG200	0.880	0.880	0.830	0.828	0.865	0.897	0.889	0.950
ECG5000	0.925	0.932	0.944	0.940	0.938	0.942	0.948	0.970
ECGFiveDays	0.797	1.000	0.984	0.999	1.000	0.996	0.997	1.000
ElectricDevices	0.631	0.587	0.747	0.736	0.776	0.890	0.898	0.732
FaceAll	0.808	0.749	0.779	0.749	0.926	0.983	0.987	0.950
FaceFour	0.898	0.966	0.852	0.998	0.941	0.939	0.967	0.976
FacesUCR	0.908	0.939	0.906	0.861	0.890	0.977	0.975	0.970
FiftyWords	0.765	0.730	0.705	0.723	0.718	0.827	0.826	0.841
Fish	0.834	0.960	0.989	0.959	0.905	0.973	0.982	0.949
FordA	0.665	0.957	0.971	0.927	0.907	0.959	0.954	0.952
FordB	0.599	0.917	0.807	0.900	0.898	0.941	0.930	0.957
GunPoint	0.913	1.000	1.000	0.995	0.957	0.995	0.999	0.980
Ham	0.600	0.667	0.686	0.764	0.772	0.850	0.859	0.868
HandOutlines	0.878	0.481	0.932	0.882	0.910	0.943	0.935	0.925
Haptics	0.416	0.468	0.523	0.460	0.439	0.537	0.547	0.655
Herring	0.531	0.625	0.672	0.619	0.618	0.625	0.626	0.831
InlineSkate	0.387	0.438	0.373	0.365	0.393	0.534	0.546	0.630
InsectWingbeatSound	0.574	0.606	0.627	0.634	0.575	0.627	0.662	0.632
ItalyPowerDemand	0.955	0.960	0.948	0.944	0.960	0.960	0.962	0.978
LargeKitchenAppliances	0.795	0.701	0.859	0.871	0.904	0.953	0.935	0.947
Lightning2	0.869	0.820	0.738	0.761	0.791	0.817	0.784	0.883
Lightning7	0.712	0.795	0.726	0.707	0.763	0.821	0.798	0.936

Table 4: Comparison of classification accuracy for ALTS, 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, GENDIS, InceptionTime, and HIVE-COTE v2.0 across 84 UEA & UCR datasets (Part II)

Dataset	1NN-DTW	LTS	ST	GRSF	GENDIS	InceptionTime	HC2	ALTS
MiddlePhalanxTW	0.506	0.506	0.519	0.632	0.631	0.527	0.592	0.735
MoteStrain	0.866	0.883	0.897	0.914	0.866	0.881	0.933	0.950
NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax1	0.829	0.259	0.950	0.917	0.894	0.958	0.955	0.954
NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax2	0.870	0.770	0.951	0.935	0.923	0.962	0.965	0.976
OliveOil	0.867	0.167	0.900	0.867	0.888	0.874	0.900	0.867
OSULeaf	0.599	0.777	0.967	0.883	0.758	0.952	0.966	0.915
PhalangesOutlinesCorrect	0.761	0.765	0.763	0.841	0.787	0.861	0.845	0.772
Plane	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.993	0.997	1.000	0.990
ProximalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.785	0.834	0.844	0.841	0.839	0.822	0.854	0.858
ProximalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.790	0.849	0.883	0.862	0.857	0.906	0.896	0.852
ProximalPhalanxTW	0.761	0.776	0.805	0.804	0.802	0.782	0.811	0.876
RefrigerationDevices	0.440	0.515	0.581	0.563	0.624	0.759	0.767	0.631
ScreenType	0.411	0.429	0.520	0.573	0.528	0.706	0.707	0.612
ShapeletSim	0.694	0.950	0.956	1.000	1.000	0.924	1.000	0.950
ShapesAll	0.802	0.768	0.842	0.790	0.793	0.938	0.934	0.844
SmallKitchenAppliances	0.672	0.664	0.792	0.806	0.742	0.771	0.841	0.759
SonyAIBORobotSurface1	0.696	0.810	0.844	0.878	0.956	0.954	0.952	0.900
SonyAIBORobotSurface2	0.859	0.875	0.934	0.912	0.870	0.951	0.947	0.960
StarLightCurves	0.898	0.947	0.979	0.977	0.953	0.978	0.982	0.967
Strawberry	0.946	0.911	0.962	0.957	0.951	0.975	0.979	0.960
SwedishLeaf	0.846	0.907	0.928	0.906	0.877	0.970	0.964	0.866
Symbols	0.938	0.932	0.882	0.933	0.925	0.970	0.971	0.960
SyntheticControl	0.983	0.997	0.983	0.993	0.987	0.996	0.998	0.990
ToeSegmentation1	0.750	0.934	0.965	0.940	0.907	0.953	0.955	0.975
ToeSegmentation2	0.908	0.915	0.908	0.885	0.906	0.964	0.960	1.000
Trace	0.990	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	1.000
TwoLeadECG	0.868	0.996	0.997	0.992	0.966	0.995	0.999	1.000
TwoPatterns	0.999	0.993	0.955	0.998	0.931	1.000	1.000	0.979
UWaveGestureLibraryAll	0.962	0.953	0.942	0.955	0.948	0.951	0.975	0.941
UWaveGestureLibraryX	0.774	0.791	0.803	0.804	0.779	0.834	0.860	0.816
UWaveGestureLibraryY	0.702	0.703	0.730	0.714	0.695	0.771	0.789	0.736
UWaveGestureLibraryZ	0.675	0.747	0.748	0.742	0.722	0.773	0.803	0.756
Wafer	0.996	0.996	1.000	1.000	0.993	0.999	1.000	0.994
Wine	0.611	0.500	0.796	0.715	0.864	0.887	0.925	0.817
WordSynonyms	0.749	0.607	0.571	0.607	0.628	0.752	0.766	0.700
Worms	0.532	0.610	0.740	0.556	0.599	0.781	0.758	0.746
WormsTwoClass	0.584	0.727	0.831	0.746	0.691	0.803	0.805	0.788
Yoga	0.843	0.834	0.818	0.838	0.802	0.912	0.930	0.850

3. ST [28]: Shapelet Transform. The method extracts a large set of candidate shapelets and converts each series into a feature vector of distances to those shapelets. A standard classifier (commonly an SVM) is then trained on the transformed feature vectors.
4. GRSF [14]: Generalized Random Shapelet Forests. GRSF builds an ensemble of decision trees that split on shapelet-based features and relies on randomized selection of instances and candidates to improve scalability.
5. GENDIS [13]: Genetic Discovery of Shapelets. GENDIS performs an evolutionary search to identify a compact, discriminative set of shapelets and optimizes selection via a genetic algorithm.
6. InceptionTime [30]: A deep convolutional model based on an inception-style architecture. The model captures multi-scale temporal patterns and often attains state-of-the-art results when trained with sufficient data and computational resources.
7. HIVE-COTE v2.0 (HC2) [23]: A heterogeneous ensemble that combines multiple classifier types and feature representations. HC2 achieves top accuracy across many UEA & UCR datasets but requires substantially more computation than single-method approaches.

5. Statistical Analysis of Results

To assess statistical significance across the 84 UEA & UCR datasets, we performed the Wilcoxon signed-rank test for paired comparisons (two-sided) between ALTS and each baseline. Table 5 reports p-values and win-loss-tie counts (ALTS wins-losses-ties) for each pairwise comparison.

At a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, ALTS significantly outperforms 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, and GENDIS ($p < 0.001$). The corresponding win-loss-tie counts are 75-8-1, 77-6-1, 59-22-3, 65-12-1, and 71-12-1, respectively. For

InceptionTime ($p = 0.913$) and HIVE-COTE v2.0 (HC2) ($p = 0.197$), the Wilcoxon test found no significant difference; the win-loss-tie counts are 38-41-5 and 24-58-2, respectively.

Table 5: Wilcoxon test results for ALTS vs. 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, GENDIS, InceptionTime, and HIVE-COTE v2.0 across 84 UEA & UCR datasets. P-values and Win-Loss-Tie ratios compare each baseline to ALTS.

Statistic	1NN-DTW	LTS	ST	GRSF	GENDIS	InceptionTime	HC2
P-Value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.913	0.197
Win-Loss-Tie	75-8-1	77-6-1	59-22-3	65-12-1	71-12-1	38-41-5	24-58-2
Average Accuracy	0.725	0.734	0.774	0.773	0.760	0.851	0.879

Note: ALTS average accuracy is **0.831**.

With a large collection of 84 datasets, pairwise tests can detect small differences. Therefore, we applied the Friedman test [33], a nonparametric rank-based procedure for comparing multiple classifiers. The Friedman test rejected the null hypothesis of equal ranks ($p < 0.001$). We followed this with the Nemenyi post hoc test [34] at significance level 0.05. The Nemenyi test yields a critical distance (CD) of 1.181.

The mean ranks are: HIVE-COTE v2.0, 2.259; ALTS, 3.089; InceptionTime, 3.133; ST, 4.620; GRSF, 4.949; LTS, 5.620; GENDIS, 5.709; and 1NN-DTW, 6.620. The Nemenyi test indicates no significant difference among 1NN-DTW, GENDIS, and LTS; among GENDIS, LTS, GRSF, and ST; and among InceptionTime, ALTS, and HIVE-COTE v2.0. Any pairwise rank difference that exceeds the CD is statistically significant. Figure 4 displays the mean ranks and the CD.

Figure 4: Average ranks of eight classifiers (ALTS, 1NN-DTW, LTS, ST, GRSF, GENDIS, InceptionTime, HIVE-COTE v2.0) based on accuracy across 84 UEA & UCR datasets, derived from the Nemenyi post-hoc test with a critical distance of 1.181.

5.1. Interpretability

Shapelet-based time-series classification methods provide an important advantage: they produce interpretable prototypes (shapelets) that correspond to concrete subsequences. Domain experts can inspect those subsequences and relate them to known phenomena, which is crucial for adoption in high-stakes domains.

As a case study on real data, we analyze the canonical ECG200 dataset using an ALTS model trained on that dataset. For each learned prototype, we computed per-instance minimum-distance scores across the dataset. Sliding windows were z -scored to match model preprocessing. We quantified prototype discrimination using the receiver operating characteristic area under the curve (ROC AUC), where larger AUC values indicate greater similarity to the target class. We also report Cohen’s d for the difference between the class distance distributions. Full per-prototype statistics and plotting scripts are available in the project repository [26].

Figure 5 displays the two prototypes that ALTS identified as most discrim-

inative for the ECG200 classes, together with representative matched subsequences. Prototype $k = 24$ is most discriminative for the Abnormal class (AUC = 0.8471, Cohen’s $d = -1.477$), indicating strong separation: Abnormal instances are substantially more similar to this prototype than are Normal instances. Prototype $k = 9$ is most discriminative for the Normal class (AUC = 0.6953, Cohen’s $d = 0.804$), indicating moderate-to-large separation in favor of Normal instances. For reference, conventional interpretation of Cohen’s d is $|d| \approx 0.2$ (small), ≈ 0.5 (medium), and $\gtrsim 0.8$ (large).

The top panels of Figure 5 show the learned prototype waveforms (z -scored for visualization). The bottom panels show representative full ECG traces with the best-matching subsequence highlighted (shaded) and overlaid (red: matched subsequence; violet: learned prototype). These visualizations provide a human-readable explanation that links local subsequences to model behavior.

Although we illustrate interpretability on ECG200 for clarity, the provided GitHub repository contains scripts and trained models for reproducing these visualizations on any of the 84 datasets, including large-scale and image-derived cases. This ensures that readers can verify interpretability across domains without expanding the article length.

All artifacts used to produce these plots (trained model, saved prototypes, per-instance feature values, `proto_stats_min_dist.csv`, and plotting scripts) are publicly available at [26].

Most Discriminative Shapelets of the ECG200 Dataset

Figure 5: Most discriminative prototypes and matched subsequences for ECG200. Top row: learned prototypes identified as most discriminative for Abnormal (left, $k = 24$) and Normal (right, $k = 9$). Bottom row: representative full time series with the best-matching subsequence highlighted (shaded) and overlaid (red: matched subsequence; violet: learned prototype). Prototype metrics: $k = 24$ (Abnormal) AUC = 0.8471, Cohen’s $d = -1.477$; $k = 9$ (Normal) AUC = 0.6953, Cohen’s $d = 0.804$. Subsequence windows are z -scored for visualization.

6. Conclusion and Discussion

This study introduced ALTS, an optimization-based framework for learning shapelets in time-series classification. ALTS learns shapelets jointly with classifier parameters using gradient-based optimization rather than by exhaustive search. The method supports multiple similarity functions (minimum, maximum, and mean squared distances, plus cosine similarity), which produce a richer and more robust feature space than minimum distance alone. ALTS also incorporates fused-lasso regularization to encourage sparse, piecewise-constant shapelets and L2 regularization to reduce overfitting. ALTS produces intrinsic, human-interpretable features in the form of shapelets. These features allow

domain experts to inspect class-specific subsequences and to link model outputs to localized temporal patterns. The model handles multi-class problems directly and does not rely on a one-vs-rest scheme, which reduces redundant computation compared with approaches that train C binary classifiers.

We evaluated ALTS on the original 84 UEA & UCR datasets (6 Device, 7 ECG, 29 Image, 14 Motion, 15 Sensor, 6 Simulated, 7 Spectro). ALTS significantly improves over several traditional shapelet baselines in pairwise tests; win-loss-tie counts versus those baselines are 75-8-1 (1NN-DTW), 77-6-1 (LTS), 59-22-3 (ST), 65-12-1 (GRSF), and 71-12-1 (GENDIS) (see Table 5). ALTS attains an average accuracy of 0.831 across the 84 datasets. This result is competitive with recent neural and ensemble methods; InceptionTime attains an average accuracy of 0.851 and HIVE-COTE v2.0 attains 0.879, as reported in Section 5.

ALTS shows especially strong performance on image-derived datasets. We attribute this advantage in part to the inclusion of cosine similarity, which provides a degree of scale and orientation invariance that benefits certain image-to-time-series representations (see Figure 1).

Limitations. ALTS has several limitations that users should consider.

- *Small-sample datasets.* On datasets with very few training instances, optimisation of discriminative shapelets can be unstable. For example, on Beef ($M = 30$, $N = 470$) ALTS underperformed relative to some search-based methods.
- *High-class-count settings.* For datasets with many classes, class separation may require more specialized shapelet representations or stronger regularization. For example, on FaceAll ($C = 14$, $N = 131$) ALTS achieved lower accuracy than a tuned deep model in our experiments.

- *Fixed candidate-length selection.* ALTS selects candidate shapelet lengths from a predefined set prior to training. The method does not currently adapt shapelet lengths dynamically during optimization, which may reduce flexibility for datasets that contain discriminative patterns at widely varying scales.

Future work. Several directions could address these limitations and extend ALTS.

- *Robust training objectives:* Integrate noise-robust losses, for example generalized cross-entropy [35], or time-series-specific label-smoothing techniques to improve resilience on noisy datasets.
- *Adaptive length learning:* Investigate mechanisms for learning shapelet lengths during training, such as differentiable alignment or explicit length-parameter gradients.
- *Multivariate and channel-wise shapelets:* Extend ALTS to multivariate series via channel-wise shapelet learning or coupled tensor factorization so that multichannel dependencies can be captured while preserving interpretability.
- *Scalability for long or streaming series:* Combine ALTS with preselection or acceleration techniques (for example, matrix profile preselection or randomized convolutional preprocessing) to reduce similarity-computation cost on long sequences or in streaming settings.
- *Class imbalance:* Develop cost-sensitive training, reweighting schemes, or data augmentation tailored to imbalanced time-series classes.

In conclusion, ALTS achieves a practical balance among interpretability, computational efficiency, and classification accuracy. Its modular design permits

joint gradient-based optimization of shapelets and classifier parameters. Non-differentiable operations (such as min/max selection and fused-lasso penalties) are handled in the current implementation via subgradient updates or smooth surrogates.

Beyond its accuracy, ALTS offers intrinsic interpretability through human-readable prototypes, as demonstrated in Section 5, which enables domain experts to directly inspect class-specific subsequences and relate them to meaningful temporal patterns.

The framework can be extended to multivariate inputs, adaptive-length shapelet learning, and resource-constrained deployment; these extensions are left for future work.

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